

Titrimetric Determination of Arsenic (III) and Antimony (III) with Potassium Chlorate

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Conditions have been established for the simple direct titrimetric determination of arsenic (III) and antimony (III) with potassium chlorate using visual indicators.

ALTHOUGH Potassium chlorate is available at a purity required for a primary standard, its potentialities as an analytical oxidant have not been worked out in detail. Earlier, the author has demonstrated the use of potassium chlorate as a primary standard oxidimetric reagent for the titrimetric determination¹⁻⁵ of Fe (II), Mo (V), Tl (I), V (III), Sn (II) and Ti (III), indigo, and thiourea. The author has now extended the applicability of potassium chlorate as a reagent for the direct titrimetric determination of As (III) and Sb (III).

Experimental

Potassium chlorate: 0.1 N potassium chlorate was prepared from 'Pro Analysis' reagent supplied by E. Merck.

Arsenic (III): 0.1 N solution of arsenic (III) was prepared from a B. D. H. Analar grade sample and standardised against cerium (IV) sulphate employing the procedure of Gleu⁶.

Antimony (III): An approximately 0.1 N antimony (III) chloride solution was prepared from a B. D. H. Analar grade sample by dissolving the requisite amount in concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluting later keeping the concentration of acid at 3M. The solution was standardised with a standard solution of potassium bromate according to the procedure of Smith⁷.

All the other reagents employed in the investigation were of Analytical reagent grade quality.

Titration of As (III)

Procedure: An aliquot of As (III) solution was taken into a 150 ml pyrex titration cell and treated

with enough concentrated hydrochloric acid and distilled water to give an overall acidity of 5-6 M at the end point when diluted to 50 ml. 5 to 8 ml of 3M potassium bromide were added and the solution was stirred well by means of a magnetic stirrer. 0.1 ml of 0.2% naphthol blue black as indicator was added and titrated with 0.1 N solution of potassium chlorate. The titration was carried out rapidly in the beginning and slowly towards the equivalence point allowing 15-20 sec., after each addition of a drop of the titrant. The end point is detected by the disappearance of the blue colour. The indicator correction is 0.04 ml of 0.1 N chlorate solution, and has to be deducted from the titre value. Some typical results obtained according to the above procedure are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF AS (III)

As(III) taken in mm.	As(III) found in mm.	Rel. Error (%)
0.1598	0.1602	0.25
0.2152	0.2147	0.23
0.2608	0.2602	0.23
0.3635	0.3626	0.25
0.4303	0.4294	0.20

Preliminary experiments conducted by the author in varying hydrochloric acid concentrations revealed that oxidation of arsenic (III) by potassium chlorate was very slow even under high acidities. Various catalysts like iodine monochloride, osmium tetroxide, potassium iodate and potassium bromide have been tried in the titration and it is found that addition of potassium bromide remarkably accelerated the reaction. The optimum conditions for the titration

are found to be 6M hydrochloric acid at the end point and 5-8 ml of 3M potassium bromide in a 50 ml of the reaction mixture. Further it is observed that hydrochloric concentration should be at least 6M for efficient functioning of the catalyst. Under lower concentrations of the catalyst than that prescribed, the reaction is rather sluggish. However, larger concentrations are without effect. The other indicators like methyl orange, methyl red, brilliant ponceau-5R, α -naphthoflavone and *p*-ethoxy chrysoidine are unsuitable in the titration. The stoichiometry of the reaction under the experimental conditions was found to be 3 moles of arsenic (III) per mole of potassium chlorate.

Titration of antimony (III) :

Accurate visual titrations of antimony (III) are possible with potassium chlorate in 6-7M hydrochloric acid using 0.1 ml. of 0.1% methyl orange, methyl red, neutral red, phenosafranine, or brilliant ponceau -5R or 0.1 ml of 0.2% naphthol blue black as indicator. The titration with potassium chlorate was made rapidly in the beginning and dropwise towards the end giving a wait 10-15 sec, between successive addition. The indicator corrections were 0.06 ml in the case of methyl orange and methyl red, 0.03 ml in the case of phenosafranine and neutral red, and no indicator corrections necessary in the case of brilliant ponceau-5R and naphthol blue black. The colour change at the end point was from red to pale yellow with methyl orange, methyl red, from blue violet to colourless through pink with phenosafranine, from violet to colourless through pink with neutral red, from blue to light

pink with naphthol blue black and from red to colourless with brilliant ponceau-5R. Of all the indicators naphthol blue black appeared to work satisfactorily, since it required no indicator correction. Some representative results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF SB (III)

Sb (III) taken in mm.	Sb (III) found in mm.	Rel. Error (%)
0.1642	0.1646	0.24
0.2644	0.2650	0.22
0.3243	0.3236	0.21
0.3909	0.3901	0.20
0.4401	0.4412	0.25

The stoichiometry of the reaction under the experimental conditions was found to be 3 moles of antimony (III) per mole of potassium chlorate.

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References

1. C. Radhakrishnamurty and G. Gopal Rao, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 254, 366.
2. G. Gopal Rao and C. Radhakrishnamurty, *B. C. S. J.*, 1972, 45, 3437.
3. C. Radhakrishnamurty and G. Gopal Rao, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 45.
4. C. Radhakrishnamurty, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, 261, 396.
5. V. V. S. Eswara Dutt and C. Radhakrishnamurty, *Analisis*, 1973, 2, 268.
6. K. Gleu, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 305.
7. G. F. Smith, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1946, 29, 143,